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WEBINAR: What exactly is bioinformatics?

7 August 2024

Material Name	Material Type (Format)	Description	URL/Persistent Identifier
What exactly is bioinformatics?	Recording (YouTube video)	Recording of the live webinar presentation	Available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel https://youtu.be/wmy2C-S-rMU
Samaha_2024_what_is_bioinformatics_webinar	Slides (PDF)	PDF copy of the slides presented during the webinar	Included in this Zenodo record